

Synthesis of 5-(2-Oxo-3-indolinyldine)-3-aryl-2-(α -hydroxy)phenylketo-4-thiazolidinones as Dyes

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Thioindigoid thiazolidinones, 5-(2-oxo-3-indolinyldine)-3-aryl-2-(α -hydroxy)phenylketo-4-thiazolidinones, obtained by condensing 3-aryl-2-(α -hydroxy)phenylketo-4-thiazolidinones with isatin, indicated as multinary products, have been studied for dyeing properties with respect to silk, polyester and cotton fibres.

The reports¹ of the dyeing properties of thioindigoid thiazolidinones, obtained by condensing generally 4-thiazolidinones with isatin, aroused our interest to synthesise and evaluate dyeing properties of some similar compounds prepared by condensing 3-aryl-2-(α -hydroxy)phenylketo-4-thiazolidinones² with isatin in dry alcohol. The results are reported in this communication. Product thioindigoid thiazolidinones, 5-(2-oxo-3-indolinyldine)-3-aryl-2-(α -hydroxy) phenylketo-4-thiazolidinones, indicated as multinary mixtures by tlc, were resolved in bulk by column chromatography and then studied.

Results and Discussion

Physical data of multinary product components are presented in Table 1.

Infrared spectra of thioindigoid thiazolidinones have displayed all the frequencies of characteristic groups³ of their reactants, 3-aryl-2-(α -hydroxy)phenylketo-4-thiazolidinones and isatin, at 1 717 (C=O ring), 1 614 (C-N), 673 (C-S-C), 1 589, 1 556, 1 532 and 1 512 (C=C aromatic), 3 438, 3 190 cm^{-1} and 2 915 (C-OH intramolecularly bonded, ν N-H and C-H) and at 1 393, 1 334, 1 270 and 1 199 cm^{-1} of (δ O-H and ν C-O enol and phenol); an additional peak at ca. 1 646 cm^{-1} observed in the spectra of almost all the compounds attributable⁴ to $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{C}}$, however, indicates condensation of pyrrole carbonyl group with thiazolidinone ring CH_2 in the products. Interestingly, a band at ca. 1 680 cm^{-1} of $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{O}}$ chain appearing only in (a) and (c) type products indicates presence of acyclic ketonic group in them, whereas in (b) and (d) type products this group

seems to be absent. The absence of acyclic (chain) carbonyl group stretching frequency in the spectra of (b) and (d) components of multinary products could only be accounted for considering the interaction of chain carbonyl group with alcoholic group of medium solvent to form ketals.

In order to check and confirm both the possibilities, fusion of thiazolidinone ring with pyrrolidinone ring and formation of ketals, as suggested above, ¹H nmr spectra of all the four components of a quaternary product of β -naphthyl-thiazolidinone as typical examples have been examined. Peaks corresponding^{3,4} to CH-N/CH-S/benzenoid ArH, non-benzenoid ArH, phenolic and C-H groups, common in all the four components of the multinary product, have been observed at τ 2.37, 1.30, 3.48 and 8.57 respectively, in their spectra. The absence of a peak due to cyclic CH_2 group, displayed at τ 6.45 by 1,4-thiazolidinones² (reactant), in their spectra, confirms condensation of thiazolidinone ring CH_2 group with pyrrolidinone ring C=O group, whereas an additional peak at τ 7.74, attributable^{3,4} to acyclic non-conjugated CH_2 group, appearing in (b) and (d) components evidently supports the formation of ketals at their acyclic carbonyl group with alcoholic group of medium solvent.

H_2SO_4 concentration necessary for producing maximum colour intensity by each dye as determined by plotting optical density (at λ_{max}) vs H_2SO_4 concentration in 200 ppm dye solution and dye colour which remained stable on fibres after different treat-

TABLE 1 – PHYSICAL DATA OF DIFFERENT COMPONENTS OF MULTINARY THIOINDIGOID DYES*

Sl. no.	Multinary mixture components	Colour of solid	M.p. °C
1.	C ₃₄ H ₂₂ N ₃ O ₆ S ₂ -C ₆ H ₅	(a) Yellow brown	> 360
2.	C ₃₈ H ₃₂ N ₃ O ₇ S ₂ -C ₆ H ₅	(b) Brown	> 360
3.	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₄ S-C ₆ H ₅	(c) Dark brown	67
4.	C ₃₄ H ₂₂ N ₃ O ₆ S ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ -SH- <i>o</i>	(a) Yellow brown	305**
5.	C ₃₈ H ₃₂ N ₃ O ₇ S ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ -SH- <i>o</i>	(b) Light mustard	>360
6.	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₄ S-C ₆ H ₄ -SH- <i>o</i>	(c) Dark brown	84
7.	C ₃₄ H ₂₁ N ₄ O ₈ S ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -NO ₂ - <i>o</i>	(a) Mustard	274***
8.	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₄ S-C ₆ H ₄ -NO ₂ - <i>o</i>	(c) Dark brown	220**
9.	C ₃₄ H ₂₁ N ₄ O ₈ S ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -NO ₂ - <i>p</i>	(a) Yellow brown	282**
10.	C ₃₈ H ₃₁ N ₄ O ₉ S ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -NO ₂ - <i>p</i>	(b) Orange	230
11.	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₄ S-C ₆ H ₄ -NO ₂ - <i>p</i>	(c) Green brown	95
12.	C ₂₂ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₅ S-C ₆ H ₄ -NO ₂ - <i>p</i>	(d) Dark brown	>360
13.	C ₃₅ H ₂₄ N ₃ O ₇ S ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -OCH ₃ - <i>o</i>	(a) Dark brown	135
14.	C ₃₉ H ₃₄ N ₃ O ₈ S ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -OCH ₃ - <i>o</i>	(b) Brown	240***
15.	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₄ S-C ₆ H ₄ -OCH ₃ - <i>o</i>	(c) Black	140**
16.	C ₃₅ H ₂₄ N ₃ O ₇ S ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -OCH ₃ - <i>m</i>	(a) Dark brown	>360
17.	C ₃₉ H ₃₄ N ₃ O ₈ S ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -OCH ₃ - <i>m</i>	(b) Light mustard	>360
18.	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₄ S-C ₆ H ₄ -OCH ₃ - <i>m</i>	(c) Yellow brown	165**
19.	C ₂₂ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₅ S-C ₆ H ₄ -OCH ₃ - <i>m</i>	(d) Red brown	202
20.	C ₃₅ H ₂₄ N ₃ O ₇ S ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -OCH ₃ - <i>p</i>	(a) Brown	>360
21.	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₄ S-C ₆ H ₄ -OCH ₃ - <i>p</i>	(c) Brown black	95
22.	C ₃₈ H ₂₄ N ₃ O ₆ S ₂ -C ₁₀ H ₇ - <i>α</i>	(a) Dark brown	>360
23.	C ₄₂ H ₃₄ N ₃ O ₇ S ₂ -C ₁₀ H ₇ - <i>α</i>	(b) Dark brown	>360
24.	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₄ S-C ₁₀ H ₇ - <i>α</i>	(c) Brown black	95
25.	C ₂₂ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₅ S-C ₁₀ H ₇ - <i>α</i>	(d) Black	>360
26.	C ₃₈ H ₂₄ N ₃ O ₆ S ₂ -C ₁₀ H ₇ - <i>β</i>	(a) Light brown	>360
27.	C ₄₂ H ₃₄ N ₃ O ₇ S ₂ -C ₁₀ H ₇ - <i>β</i>	(b) Dark brown	>360
28.	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₄ S-C ₁₀ H ₇ - <i>β</i>	(c) Brown black	97
29.	C ₂₂ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₅ S-C ₁₀ H ₇ - <i>β</i>	(d) Dark brown	190
30.	C ₃₈ H ₃₁ N ₄ O ₆ S ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -N(C ₂ H ₅) ₂ - <i>p</i>	(a) Dark brown	290
31.	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₄ S-C ₆ H ₄ -N(C ₂ H ₅) ₂ - <i>p</i>	(c) Black	72

*All compounds gave satisfactory N analysis. **Decomposed (a), (c) and (b), (d) are high-*R_f* and low-*R_f* components respectively, of both acetone-insoluble and -soluble fractions. D, decompose. ***Sublimed.

ments are reported in Table 2. These compounds which exhibit high potential as acid dyes by imparting stable shiny colours, high total dye exhaustion and fixation to silk fibre could be used in apparel industry. For cotton and polyester fibres total dye exhaustion and fixation values, ca. 54% and 79%, and ca. 28% and 48%, 850

were too low to recommend these compounds as dyes.

Experimental

3-Aryl-2-(α-hydroxy)phenylketo-4-thiazolidinones² and their thioindigoid thiazolidinones: A mixture containing thioglycolic acid and ketoanil (0.01 mol of each or 1 : 2 mole ratio in bis-ketoanils) in benzene was refluxed for 15–20 h. Reaction mixture was then concentrated by evaporation and neutralised with aqueous solution of sodium bicarbonate to remove unreacted acid. The solid obtained was washed with water and dried in hot air oven at ~ 60° to yield 3-aryl-2-(α-hydroxy)phenylketo-4-thiazolidinones.

For the preparation of thioindigoid thiazolidinones, a mixture of 5-(2-oxo-3-indolinyldene)-3-aryl-2-(α-hydroxy)phenylketo-4-thiazolidinones, 3-aryl-2-(α-hydroxy)phenylketo-4-thiazolidinones (0.016 mol), isatin (0.016 mol) and fused anhydrous sodium acetate (0.016 mol) in absolute alcohol was refluxed for 30–35 h. The yellow brown reaction mixture was then poured into water (400 ml) and the resulting orange or yellow-brown solid was washed with water, alcohol and carbon tetrachloride successively, and dried in a hot air-oven at ~ 60°.

Homogeneity test and resolution of multinary products: All the thioindigoid thiazolidinones were dissolved in acetone and the insoluble solid filtered out. The residue obtained after evaporation of filtrate to dryness was dried in hot air-oven. For testing homogeneity and for finding out resolving solvents of insoluble and soluble fractions their solutions in dimethylformamide and acetone respectively, were run on silica gel thin layers using various one- and two-component developing solvents. Tlc test revealed that both insoluble and soluble fractions contained two components in most of the instances.

Both, acetone-soluble and -insoluble fractions revealed as binary mixtures, were resolved in bulk by column chromatography conducted in glass columns of different sizes according to quantity of mixture available using silica gel (50–100 mesh, B.D.H.) and benzene-ethanol (2 : 3, v/v) and n-butanol as developing solvents; loading solvents for these fractions were acetone and dimethylformamide respectively. Fast-mov-

TABLE 2 - α_{\max} , MINIMUM H₂SO₄ CONCENTRATION FOR DYING, FIBRE COLOURS, DYE EXHAUSTION AND FIXATION

Compd.		λ_{\max} in aqueous acidic solution	H ₂ SO ₄ reqd. for max. colour intensity	Total dye exhaustion*	Fixation* of dye to the fibre	Treated silk fibre colour
		nm	ppm	%	(%)	
C ₃₄ H ₂₂ N ₃ O ₆ S ₂ -C ₆ H ₅	(a)	425	4.9	60.2	87.6	Light brown
C ₃₄ H ₂₂ N ₃ O ₆ S ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ -SH- <i>o</i>	(a)	505	4.9	69.8	88.8	Brown yellow
C ₃₄ H ₂₁ N ₄ O ₈ S ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -NO ₂ - <i>o</i>	(a)	435	122.5	70.2	88.0	Yellow
C ₃₄ H ₂₁ N ₄ O ₈ S ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -NO ₂ - <i>p</i>	(a)	425	122.5	66.6	89.8	Brown
C ₃₅ H ₂₄ N ₃ O ₇ S ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -OCH ₃ - <i>o</i>	(a)	515	122.5	71.6	93.8	Wine brown
C ₃₅ H ₂₄ N ₃ O ₇ S ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -OCH ₃ - <i>p</i>	(a)	490	122.5	73.0	95.6	Dark brown
C ₃₈ H ₂₄ N ₃ O ₆ S ₂ -C ₁₀ H ₇ - α	(a)	530	122.5	68.5	89.2	Brown
C ₃₈ H ₂₄ N ₃ O ₆ S ₂ -C ₁₀ H ₇ - β	(a)	535	122.5	58.9	86.4	Light brown
C ₃₈ H ₃₁ N ₄ O ₆ S ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -N(C ₂ H ₅) ₂ - <i>p</i>	(a)	500	122.5	63.8	88.2	Brown

*Dye exhaustion and fixation values are average of results obtained from both methods.

ing (high R_f) component collected and slow-moving (low R_f) component eluted with dimethylformamide of each binary set were obtained as solids on evaporation of their eluates. In some cases low R_f component was too low to collect.

Melting points of the compounds were determined in open glass capillaries and are uncorrected. Infrared spectra (nujol) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer, nmr spectra (DMSO) on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 spectrophotometer and electronic spectra on a Bausch and Lomb spectronic-20 spectrophotometer.

For the determination of workable wavelength (λ_{\max}), acidic solutions of dyes were prepared by dissolving suitable quantity in dilute H₂SO₄. But for finding the necessary H₂SO₄ concentration for maximum colour intensity (absorbance) of a dye, five equiconcentrate (200 ppm) solutions of each sample in sulphuric acid of varying concentrations (216, 137, 123, 5 and 1.2 ppm) were prepared and their optical densities determined at λ_{\max} of the dye.

Two of the four pre-washed white cloth pieces (5 × 5 cm) of silk, polyester and cotton were dipped in a dye (high R_f , (a)-component of acetone-insoluble fraction of multinary product) solution (200 ppm) at room temperature (32 ± 1°) and at ~ 90° containing requisite JICS-2

amount of H₂SO₄ and were left for 30–45 min, squeezed and dried in sunlight. One piece of each fibre, dyed by cold and hot methods, was washed with water, liquid soap (Ezee brand), detergent cake (Rin brand) and detergent powder (Surf brand) respectively, and dried in sunlight. Cloths were pressed at nylon, S. art, soie, laine, cotton and linen pressing temperatures and colour changes, if any, were recorded.

For determining total dye exhaustion, two pre-washed white cloth pieces (15 × 15 cm) of silk, polyester and cotton were dyed in acidic solution of each dye (200 ppm) by both the methods as usual. One piece of each fibre dyed by each method was squeezed and volume and optical density of the extracted solution was measured to deduce concentration from its calibration curve prepared under similar conditions of temperature (28 ± 2°) and solvent; from the concentration of extract, total dye exhaustion was calculated. Dyed dry cloths were dipped in water (100–150 ml) and left there in for 30 min and then squeezed; this process was repeated for 5–6 times. After last squeezing, concentration of the extract was determined to find out the fixation of dye to the fibre.

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